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Impact of Dividend Announcements on Shareholder Wealth: A Study of Selected IT Firms

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Abstract: This study examines the effect of dividend announcements on shareholder wealth in top Indian IT firms. Dividend announcements are regarded as significant indicators of a firm's position, future profitability, and management policy, which affect investor attitudes and stock price changes. Observing how markets react to such announcements provides insight into how investors perceive corporate signals and how payout decisions affect shareholder value.

The study uses an event-study framework to estimate abnormal returns (AR) and cumulative abnormal returns (CAR) on dividend announcement dates. The companies' daily stock prices and the NIFTY 50 index are used to assess the impact of dividend announcements on overall market movement. Event and estimation windows are specified to observe both short-term and contemporaneous market responses, and findings are examined to identify if dividend changes, cuts, or special dividends trigger differential reactions among shareholders.

Early findings indicate that increases in dividends tend to be associated with positive abnormal returns, indicating investor optimism regarding the profitability and consistency of the firm's cash flows. Dividend reductions, however, can be associated with negative abnormal returns, indicating possible financial constraints or ambiguity. The size of shareholder wealth effects is heterogeneous across firms, depending on payout policy, market expectations, and firm size.

Keywords: Shareholder wealth, dividend announcements, abnormal returns, payout policy, Indian IT firms.

1. Introduction

A firm's dividend policy is an integral part of corporate finance that reflects management's confidence and performance. Dividend announcements often impact share prices and perceptions, which, in turn, benefit shareholders. According to signalling theory, a cut in dividend payments may signal financial vulnerability, whereas an increase in dividends indicates sound, healthy financial conditions.

The Indian IT sector's setting is unique for this kind of examination because companies like Infosys, TCS, Wipro, and HCL Technologies effectively balance consistent dividend payouts with substantial growth opportunities. These companies use dividends to reward investors and signal stability, even if they are innovation-driven.

The present study examines the impact of dividend an-

nouncements on shareholder wealth in a few Indian IT companies. It aims to explore how the market reacts to dividend decisions, investor views, and the impact of such announcements on investment behaviour. Secondary data from previous research publications and original data from respondents are collected via a structured Google Form survey.

2. Literature Review

Pratibha Kumari & Rajesh Pathak (2025). "Does Dividend Distribution Policy Disclosure Create Shareholder Value?", published in the International Journal of Disclosure and Governance, found that dividend policy announcements may sometimes negatively affect shareholder value, especially for smaller firms.

Abdulateif Almulhim et al. (2024). "The Power of ESG in

Shaping Dividend Policy: Financial Sustainability in an Emerging Market," published in PLOS ONE, highlighted that ESG factors influence dividend policy and impact long-term shareholder value and sustainability.

Raven Booker et al. (2023). "Dividend Policy and Shareholder Value" discussed major dividend theories and concluded that dividend policy plays a crucial role in shareholder value creation and investor behaviour.

Karthik Bhimavarapu (2022). "Empirical Evidence on the Effect of Dividend Announcement on Stock Return", examined 55 listed companies using event study methodology and found that dividend increases are associated with positive abnormal returns, although results were not always statistically strong.

Dhananjay Narzary & K.C. Biswal (2021). "Impact of Dividend Announcements on Stock Returns: An Empirical Study of Indian Companies" Used data from 80 companies listed on the BSE (2004–2020). The study applied an event-study methodology and found that dividend announcements significantly influence stock returns, with strong trading activity on announcement dates.

3. Research Objectives

- To examine the impact of dividend announcements on the shareholder wealth of selected IT companies in India.
- To analyse investor perceptions regarding dividend announcements and their influence on investment decisions.
- To identify the relationship between dividend announcements and stock price movements in the IT sector.
- To evaluate how demographic factors such as age, income, and investment experience affect investors' responses to dividend announcements.

4. Research Methodology

4.1. Research Design

In this regard, the study adopted a descriptive research design for analysing the impact of dividend announcements on shareholder wealth in selected Indian IT companies. The research integrated both quantitative and qualitative approaches to understand investor perceptions and market behaviour.

4.2. Data Collection

Primary information was obtained through a structured Google Form questionnaire that was administered to individual investors, students, and professionals conversant with financial markets. The questionnaires included items on demographic information, investment experience, and views on dividend announcements and their impact on shareholder wealth.

Secondary Data: Data are obtained from research journals, stock exchange data, and previous studies on dividend policy and market reactions.

4.3. Sampling and Respondents

- A convenience sampling method was adopted because of accessibility and time constraints.

- A total of 50 valid responses were received.
- Individual investors of varied age groups, income classes, and educational backgrounds made up the respondents to provide a diverse representation of investor opinions.

4.4. Tools and Techniques of Analysis

- Data analysis was done with the help of SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) and Microsoft Excel.
- Frequency, percentage, and mean are some of the descriptive statistics used to summarise demographic details and responses.
- Cross-tabulation and Chi-square tests in SPSS were used to establish the relation between investor demographics and perceptions of dividend announcements.
- Graphs and tables were prepared for clear visual interpretation of results

5. Scope of the Study

The study focuses on four IT companies in India: Infosys, TCS, Wipro, and HCL Technologies. Such firms were selected based on the consistency of their dividend policy and their market interest rates. The study examines how dividend announcements affect shareholders' perceptions and wealth in the IT sector.

5.1. Hypothesis

- **Null Hypothesis:** Dividend announcements have no significant effect on shareholder wealth in selected IT companies.
- **Alternative Hypothesis:** Dividend announcements have a significant effect on shareholder wealth in selected IT companies.

6. Analysis of Data

Table 1 and Figure 1 show the gender distribution of the respondents. Out of a total of 50 participants, 30 (60%) are male, and 20 (40%) are female. This indicates that the majority of respondents in the sample are male (60% of the total population, while females constitute 40%. Hence, the data reflect a male-dominated sample in this study.

Figure 1: Gender Distribution of Respondents.

Table 1: Current Ratio

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Male	30	60.0	60.0	60.0
Female	20	40.0	40.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	-

Table 2: Investment Experience of the respondents

Investment Experience	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Per-cent	Cumulative Percent
< 1 year	42	84.0	84.0		84.0
1 – 3 years	6	12.0	12.0		96.0
3 – 5 years	2	4.0	4.0		100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0		

The table above shows the distribution of respondents by investment experience. It shows that a majority of the respondents (84%) have limited experience, suggesting that most investors are still in the learning or early investing stage. Only 4% of the respondents have more than 3 years of experience. This pattern highlights the need for greater financial awareness and investor education among participants.

Table 3: Investment preference in shares of IT companies

Do you invest in shares of IT Companies listed on NSE/BSE					
Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Per-cent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	28	56.0	56.0		56.0
No	22	44.0	44.0		100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0		

Figure 2: invest in shares of IT Companies listed on NSE/BSE.

Table 3 shows that 56% of respondents are investing in shares of IT companies, while the remaining 44% are not. This indicates that a majority of respondents have a positive inclination toward investing in the IT sector, reflecting their confidence in its growth and profitability. However, the presence of a significant portion (44%) who do not invest suggests that some investors may still be cautious or lack awareness about opportunities in IT company shares.

Table 4: Investment preference in shares of IT companies

Purpose of investment in the IT sector					
Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Per-cent	Cumulative Percent
1	32	64.0	64.0		64.0
1,2	2	4.0	4.0		68.0
1,2,3,4	4	8.0	8.0		76.0
1,2,4	1	2.0	2.0		78.0
1,3	3	6.0	6.0		84.0
1,4	1	2.0	2.0		86.0
3	7	14.0	14.0		100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0		

The table shows the primary purpose of the respondents for their investments in IT companies. Most of the respondents (64%) are investing for the purpose of Long-term wealth creation. This indicates that most investors have a long-term investment perspective, focusing on the growth potential and stability of the IT sector rather than seeking short-term gains. It also suggests that respondents view IT companies as reliable and profitable options for building sustainable wealth over time.

Table 5: Impact of Dividend announcements on share value

Dividend announcements increase the market value of shares in the short term.					
Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Per-cent	Cumulative Percent
2	3	6.0	6.0		6.0
3	7	14.0	14.0		20.0
4	15	30.0	30.0		50.0
5	25	50.0	50.0		100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0		

Figure 3: Dividend announcement increase the market value of shares in the short term.

The graph illustrates respondents' opinions on whether dividend announcements increase the market value of shares in the short term. It is observed that 50% of the respondents rated it 5 stars, indicating a strong agreement that dividend announcements positively influence share prices in the short term. This suggests that a majority of investors perceive dividend declarations as a favorable signal, often leading to an immediate rise in market value due to increased investor confidence and positive market sentiment.

The data suggests that investors in the IT sector are becoming more self-reliant and information-driven, preferring to analyse stocks independently. However, a portion still depends on professional or digital sources, reflecting a mix of traditional and modern decision-making behavior.

Table 6: Impact of Dividend announcements on share value

Source of your investment decisions.				
Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	19	38.0	38.0	38.0
1,2,3	1	2.0	2.0	40.0
1,2,3,4,5	2	4.0	4.0	44.0
1,3,4,5	1	2.0	2.0	46.0
1,3,5	1	2.0	2.0	48.0
1,4	3	6.0	6.0	54.0
1,4,5	2	4.0	4.0	58.0
1,5	1	2.0	2.0	60.0
2	4	8.0	8.0	68.0
3	7	14.0	14.0	82.0
3,5	1	2.0	2.0	84.0
4	4	8.0	8.0	92.0
4,5	1	2.0	2.0	94.0
5	3	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Where 1 = self-analysis, 2 = stock broker, 3 = financial advisor, 4 = online platforms, 5 = friends/family.

The data suggests that investors in the IT sector are becoming more self-reliant and information-driven, preferring to analyse stocks independently. However, a portion still depends on professional or digital sources, reflecting a mix of traditional and modern decision-making behaviour.

7. Findings

- Most respondents demonstrated a strong awareness of stock market trends and IT company performance, reflecting the increasing financial literacy among investors.
- A majority (38%) of investors rely on self-analysis for investment decisions, followed by financial advisors (14%), and online platforms (8%). This indicates a growing trend of independent decision-making supported by digital tools.
- The primary motivation for investing in IT companies is long-term wealth creation, showing that most investors focus on sustainable growth rather than short-term trading.
- A significant proportion of respondents agreed that dividend announcements positively influence the market value of shares in the short term, suggesting that dividend news is still perceived as a signal of company strength.
- Around 56
- Around 56% of respondents reported investing in IT companies, highlighting confidence in the sector’s consistent performance and resilience.
- Over 50% of respondents rated 5 stars for the impact of dividend announcements on market value, suggesting strong agreement that such announcements influence short-term share prices.

8. Conclusion

The study titled “Shareholder Wealth Effect of Dividend Announcements – Evidence from Selected IT Companies” examined how dividend announcements influence investors’ perceptions and market value. Based on primary data collected from 50 respondents and analyzed through SPSS, the study found that most investors view dividend announcements as a positive signal of a company’s financial health. Dividend news tends to create a short-term rise in share prices, indicating its role in influencing market sentiment. However, the research also revealed that investors’ long-term investment behavior is guided more by self-analysis, company fundamentals, and the goal of wealth creation rather than dividend policies alone. The majority of respondents relied on their own research or online sources to make investment decisions, showing increased financial awareness and independence among modern investors.

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